

Tasks on the development of students' speech and thinking in the primary language and reading literacy classes

Shavkatova Shakhrizoda Shavkatovna

Navoi State Pedagogical institute speciality of 'methodology and theory of education and upbringing' (primary school) 2nd year of master's degree student

Abstract – This article discusses the importance of tasks in the development of oral and written speech of primary school students, as well as their thinking. Emphasis is placed on the use of assignments in the course of the lesson.

Keywords – speech, thinking, written speech, oral speech, assignments, retelling, education, science, mother tongue, vocabulary.

Simultaneous development of students' oral and written speech is an urgent issue of primary language education. Because it is impossible to become a person of high spirituality and culture without knowing your native language perfectly. The development of a system of practical exercises and tasks based on scientific and methodical methods aimed at developing the speech culture and thinking of schoolchildren is an important requirement of today.

The task is a manifestation of the knowledge and rich experience of humanity accumulated over several centuries. The appearance of tasks also goes back to a long history. This important tool has been relied upon for centuries in the teaching process, and its systematic use in education will continue to be important.

Assignment is a broad concept that is used in many areas of human activity. We repeatedly refer to the assignment in connection with production, household life and general circulation. The educational task, which is widely used in education, is considered an important tool in teaching all subjects. Assignments are extremely important in mother tongue classes. It performs several tasks in the educational process:

- educational assignments are an important means of equipping students with the knowledge, skills and abilities that they develop in the formation of speech and thinking in primary school mother tongue classes. Knowledge is transferred to students' activities through assignments and it is mastered thoroughly. Also, the knowledge acquired through the assignment becomes a product of the student's practical activity, and he can freely use this knowledge in any place, that is, in familiar and unfamiliar conditions.

- educational assignments are considered a means of education and development of the student. With the help of assignments, the student develops a love for the language and makes a bold commitment to study it diligently. Assignments play an important role in shaping the student's outlook, preparing them for work and independent life. Through assignments, the student learns to overcome learning

difficulties with perseverance and perseverance, to work independently and to increase his knowledge independently. Educational tasks in the native language class greatly help in the formation and development of the student's individual-psychic characteristics: memory, will, character, abilities.

- tasks also serve as a means of activating students' activities. The system of tasks in the subject of the mother tongue requires independent completion by each student. The process of independent thinking, thinking, searching for the unknown is an active process. Any type of assignment requires a certain level of research and thinking from the student. And the search does not come to the surface without active activity.

Psychologists and Methodist scientists are interested in this issue because of the incomparable importance of raising the quality of educational tasks in the formation of students' speech and thinking in the primary class mother tongue classes, in educating and developing the personality, and activating his practical activity. There are different approaches to learning tasks in science.

Tasks that require expressive reading in the course of mother tongue lessons are also one of the most important means of improving student performance. If the materials selected for the assignments are not only in the native language program, but also if the topics that are not in the program, but are suitable for the age characteristics of the students, a positive result can be obtained from the assignment. Such assignments:

- a) introduces students to the rich possibilities of the native language;
- b) forms expressive reading skills in them;
- c) has an effective effect on the development of students' speech;
- g) increases his interest in assignments.

Creative tasks are the process of memorizing, creating new knowledge, applying the knowledge, skills and abilities received in the process of generalization independently in different conditions. In our opinion, it is appropriate that 30% of the tasks given in the course of mother tongue lessons should be occupied by practical works at the level of recollection, and the rest should be occupied by partly creative and mainly creative works. Then we will be able to educate not only an 'educated' person who has learned a number of rules and concepts of the native language, but also a creative and active person with a creative mind. Therefore, mother tongue education should aim at cultivating a creative thinker who knows the language.

Although the concepts of 'educated person' and 'creative thinker' are close to each other in terms of content, they are fundamentally different from each other. A person who knows a lot is called an educated person. However, it should not be forgotten that human memory is limited, and it can never have unlimited knowledge and information. Therefore, when using the concept of 'knowledgeable', we must not forget the limitation of this knowledge. 'Creative thinker' is a much broader concept

than 'educated person'. He is not only an educated person, but also a person who has learned the ways of knowing, who can expand what he knows, and who can freely apply his knowledge in his practical activities.

If we compare a knowledgeable person to a person who memorizes a hundred thousand lines of poetry, but cannot analyze it, a creative thinker can be compared to a person who memorizes a small amount of poetry, but can analyze it, has artistic recitation skills, and dies from poems. Can be compared to a person who can freely use it in his practical activities. The first person can memorize a hundred thousand lines of poetry, and the second person can easily analyze an unlimited number of poems. Therefore, the possibilities of the first person are limited, while the possibilities of the second are unlimited.

Each of the non-traditional tasks has a number of opportunities for improving the activity of students.

1. Research tasks. In primary class mother tongue lessons, students use tasks aimed at gaining new knowledge by understanding the meaning of words, interpreting their meaning, observing events, comparing, summarizing, and comparing similarities and differences.

2. Assignments of a practical nature. This type of assignments arouses great interest in students. The important thing about practical tasks is that it brings students into problem situations.

3. Assignments aimed at increasing students' self-esteem arouse great interest in students and have an effective effect on the activation of their educational activities. Students are required to explain the meaning of some words found in the assignments.

4. Tasks related to working with text, changing text and creating text. Tasks such as describing a text in a certain style in another style, identifying their similarities and differences by comparing topics, and creating a text suitable for the purpose are among the tasks that serve to develop students' speech, and they are students' has an effective effect on increasing cognitive activity.

Another type of non-traditional educational tasks that serve to develop students' speech and thinking in mother tongue classes are game tasks. This type of tasks requires research, knowledge, resourcefulness and speed from the student. Games and tasks ensure an interesting passage of mother tongue lessons. 'Which group is the winner', 'This book is ours', 'The words are ours, the composition is yours', 'I started the text, you continue'.

In mother tongue and reading literacy lessons, game tasks aimed at developing attention, will and intelligence can also be used. For example, games such as 'Remember the order of words', 'Test your memory' to strengthen memory, and 'Think of it' to increase ingenuity and intelligence are of great importance.

'Journey to the World of Learned or Learned Knowledge' lessons are also important in the formation of students' speaking skills in primary-grade mother tongue classes.

The teacher divides the educational tasks given during the lesson into four or five parts. A student who overcomes learning difficulties in a certain part goes to the second part under the guidance of the teacher. Students who overcome all learning difficulties conquer the land of knowledge.

Thus, the content of education is also expressed in educational tasks, effective and appropriate use of traditional and non-traditional tasks, students' speech and wider use of educational tasks that serve to form and develop thinking has an effective effect on the activation of student activity. Especially problem tasks, creative tasks are important in ensuring students' activity. Interesting educational tasks aimed at developing students' speech and thinking are an important tool in mother tongue and reading literacy classes. Appropriate and proper use of handouts will help the teacher achieve high results in a short period of time. In addition to learning, students develop such qualities as independence, creativity, self-examination and evaluation of their own knowledge, self-confidence, responsibility for solving each task, and a conscious approach with creativity.

References

1. G'ulomov A., Kasimov M., Ernazarova M. Mother tongue teaching methodology. - Tashkent: Science and technology, 2012. - 379 p.
2. DTS and curriculum of general secondary education. T.: 2017. -74 p.
3. Sariyev Sh. Start internal education - a solid foundation of education // Increase the quality and efficiency of the educational process by modernizing Start internal education. -Tashkent: Reliable print, 2016. - p. 76.
4. Methodology of development of speech and thinking through independent education in elementary school students: monograph / H. Bakiyeva. - Tashkent: 'TRUSTABLE PARTNER', 2021. - 112 p.